

**Nightlife Tourism and Nighttime Economy:
An Insight into Francophone African Cities**

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Abstract:

This study addresses “nighttime economy and nightlife tourism as two distinctive aspects of tourism development in Francophone Africa. The Cyclical Theory of Nightlife (CTN) and Actor-Network Theory (ANT) are being used to show the changing dimensions in nightlife tourism and the relationships that exist between the two phenomena. The study area is Lomé in Togo and Abidjan in Cote d’Ivoire. The survey research design was employed to identify the similarity and difference between nightlife patrons visit dimensions and nighttime economy, and the correlation coefficient test statistic was deployed for hypothesis test. Results show that there is visible transformation in nightlife tourism which has had considerable impact on nighttime economy in both cities.

Keywords: Nightlife tourism, Nighttime economy, Nightlife destinations, Nighttime business

Résumé

Cette étude porte sur «Nightlife tourisme-tourisme de la vie nocturne» et «Nighttime economy – économie de la vie nocturne» comme deux aspects distinctifs du développement touristique en Afrique francophone. La théorie cyclique de la vie nocturne (CTN) et acteur-Network Théorie (ANT) sont utilisés pour montrer les dimensions changeantes du tourisme de la vie nocturne et les relations qui existent entre les deux phénomènes. La zone d’étude est Lomé au Togo et Abidjan en Côte d’Ivoire. La conception de la recherche de l’enquête a été utilisée pour identifier la similitude et la différence entre les clients de la vie et économie nocturne, et la statistique de test de coefficient de corrélation a été déployée pour le test d’hypothèse. Les résultats montrent qu’il existe une transformation visible dans le tourisme de la vie nocturne qui a eu un impact considérable sur l’ économie de nuit dans les deux villes.

Mots clés: Tourisme de la vie nocturne, Economie de la vie nocturne, Destinations nocturnes, Affaires de la vie nocturne.

Introduction

The improvement in living standards across the globe largely due to technological advancement, medicine and other commercial activities have made most urban settlements have the potency of a 24hour lifestyle. This push-factor has made the orthodox 9-5 work and/or leisure period insufficient, hence an expansion into dusk till the early hours of the morning. Commercial and/or leisure activities beyond usual day time are components of night time economy and nightlife tourism respectively.

Specifically, Nighttime economy describes the tangible and intangible government and private economic indicators that operate for revenue at night, to include; the number of employment opportunities presented by nightlife business, government revenue realized from night time business, number of nightclubs, bars, restaurants, live shows/concerts or carnivals, night transportation, social activities, hard drugs and so on. Nightlife tourism on the other hand describes the demographics and intentions of night time tourists/patrons as well as the products offered by night time businesses.

Nightlife tourism precedes night time economy, because without the willingness and ability of people to extend their leisure search into the night there would be no night time economy. Also, Entrepreneurs identify opportunities to establish nighttime infrastructures on the basis of perceived night life patronage. Nightlife tourism has therefore become an inevitable phenomenon of contemporary societies due to the potency of movement towards a 24hour environment. It is on the basis of the above that this study investigates nightlife tourism and nighttime economy using Francophone Africa cities.

Problem Statement

Nightlife tourism has often been used interchangeably with nighttime economy by most researchers. Although there is a significant difference, the former refers to the demographic configuration and the intrinsic and extrinsic motive of tourists visit intensity and frequency to nightlife destinations. While the latter refers to everything within and around the nighttime environment that relates to income/revenue generation, assets, liabilities, employment, policy/regulations or guidelines, etc. that emerge out of the nightlife tourism patronage intensity and frequency. Thus this study intends to clarify the disparity. Furthermore, nightlife tourism has not received sufficient investigation particularly in Francophone Africa. Past studies have focused predominantly on tourism in general and its effect on socio-economic development, without attempting to particularize their investigation into nighttime economic development as consequent to nightlife tourism.

Nightlife tourism and nighttime economy is perceived to be concentrated around nightclubs, bars and restaurants. There is usually almost no nightclub in most of the francophone towns like Lomé, Abidjan, Yaoundé etc. that are not in close proximity to a restaurant or a bar as will be shown later in the study. This connection and concentration of night time business and paucity of scholarly information identified beforehand constitute the grounds upon which this study is designed to accommodate as well as proffer realistic and long-term solutions thereof.

Study Objectives

1. The broad objectives of this research activity is to investigate nightlife tourism and nighttime economy in Francophone African cities from 2008 – 2017.
2. Determine the relationship between nightlife tourism and nighttime economy in Lomé and Abidjan from 2008 – 2017
3. Determine the co-variation between nightlife patron visit dimension and the development of nighttime economy in Lomé and Abidjan from 2008 – 2017

Research Questions

The following questions stated below emerged out of the need to achieve the specific research objectives. They are as follows;

- i. What is the relationship between nightlife tourism and nighttime economy in Lomé and Abidjan from 2008 – 2017?
- ii. What is the co-variation between nightlife patrons visit dimensions and the development of night time economy in Lomé and Abidjan from 2007-2017?

Research Hypotheses

Three hypothesis are enumerated in a bid to find answers to the research questions as well as to achieve the specific objectives of the study. They are stated in null (*H₀*) form below

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between nightlife tourism and night time economy in Lomé and Abidjan from 2008 – 2017.

Hypothesis 2

There is no co-variation between nightlife patrons visit dimension and the development of night time economy in Lomé and Abidjan from 2009 – 2017

Empirical review

Hadfield & Newton (2010) studied “Alcohol, crime and disorder in the night-time economy from an exploratory perspective in England from 1999-2009. The findings showed that nightlife tourism in UK was heavily associated with alcohol abuse, crime etc. dominated by young adults between the ages of 18-35 years, though no documented evidence of escalating crime rate over the period studied. Furthermore, the findings revealed that night time economy in UK was practically increasing in terms of the number of nightclubs, pubs, bars, restaurants, live shows/concerts etc. and this increase presented potentials for improving government revenue, employment opportunities, entrepreneurship investments and so on.

Similarly, Elvis & Hadfield (2003) in West end ‘stress area night-time economy profiling’ attempted to utilize not only data from public security systems but from respondents directly engaged in commercial activities within the nighttime economy in UK, in a bid to unfold a clearer co-variation between the activities of nightlife and its positive and/or negative effect on the immediate community. The study attempted to underscore the effect of nightlife tourism and nighttime economy on patrons, investors, government, local residents and workers. Both primary and secondary sources of data were used in carrying out the study, thus the survey research design was eminent. Semi-structured interview sessions were applied by the investigator for retrieving primary data, while secondary sources of data were retrieved from the West trimerster community protection team, West trimerster crime and Disorder Reduction Partnership, Metropolitan police service, West trimerster CCTV etc. The major infrastructures of the nighttime economy in the study area include pubs, wine bars, licensed and unlicensed nightclubs. The findings showed that there was adequate and regular monitoring and control of nightlife tourism and night time

economy in the study area and that adequate documentation was key in regimenting the night time economy. The study recommended among other things ensuring up-to-date location data on alcoholic beverage selling businesses in the nighttime economy, integrating a quick response facility ambulance and integrating public security police in establishing a secure crime profile data-base.

Poolay, Hadfield & Houghton (2017) attempted a quantitative approach to Hackey's evening and nighttime economy using the break-even analysis technique. The study compartmentalized night time economy into three (3) categories to include (i) core: food, drink and entertainment (ii) indirect: accommodation, retail, parking and cabs (iii) support: care, infrastructure and public communicating. The break-even analysis was in respect of the amount of government expenditure on policing and justice services, ambulance and hospital services, subsidized services on transportation and other local authority services like lighting, street cleaning, parking, live events/show management etc.

The specific objectives of the study were to bring to birth a logical economic related analysis of evening and night life economy in terms of the number of nighttime investment specifics, government revenue from night time economy and nightlife tourism in the area. The findings showed that there were one thousand three hundred and seventy-five (1375) firms operating in Harckey's nighttime economy, with four thousand seven hundred and twenty (4,720) employment and two hundred and nineteen (219) million pounds as expenditure. The study observed that the central government revenue on value added tax (VAT) for gambling duties was 40.5 million pounds, Excise (alcohol) duty, income tax, corporate tax and business rates in 2017 were 6.28, 32.95, 5.19 and 6.20 million pounds respectively. The break-even analysis result showed that for every one pound spent by the central government for monitoring and control of nighttime economy it receives a revenue of 3.97 pounds i.e. close to four times of what is invested returns back as proceeds. The study concluded that there were positive returns presented by Harckney's nighttime economy and that greater efforts should be made by the cultural grant in a bid to attract more private investment into the particular sector. The recommendations made included among other things, increased grant focus in the nighttime economy that presents nominal costs and greater revenue.

Shemes and Ghadban (2015) utilized the stakeholder approach as a philosophical baseline in capturing "nightlife tourism" in terms of its positive and negative effects on host communities, while particularizing the phenomenon in Gemmayzeh, Lebanon, The research problem was built upon the concern that public policy formulation and implementation concerning the control, monitoring and advancement of night time economy and its infrastructure did not integrate sufficient ideas, opinions and suggestions from both local residents and indigenous personalities, thereby depleting indigenous cultural heritage vis-à-vis ancient historical buildings/monuments.

The socio-cultural impacts of nightlife tourism and host community perceptions of nightlife tourism were the primary focal point of the conceptual and empirical review. The survey research design was adopted for the investigation and thus relied heavily on both primary and secondary data sources. Primary sources were gotten via copies of questionnaire administered, while secondary data sources were gotten from corporate

documents and the local council authority in Gemmayzeh, Lebanon. The population of the study comprised of 1,400 permanent residents and 50 foreign respondents were used as sample for inductive reasons. Four hypotheses were developed in the course of achieving the counteractive solutions to the perceived research problem. The chi-square test statistic on a two-way contingency was deployed for the hypotheses test. The test unfolded that “the increasing negative impacts of tourism in Gemmayzeh have significantly affected the perceptions of residents towards tourism development in general “The test further revealed that “the negatively perceived tourism impacts did not contribute to local resident’s rejection of nightlife tourism development in Gemmyazeh. Furthermore, the result from hypothesis 4 test showed that the higher the educational level of local residents the less they tend to support tourism development in the study area. The study recommended the development of other tourism dimensions that attempt to amplify indigenous cultures as well as the integration of local residents into the formulation and implementation process of tourism policies.

Impact of night carnival activities toward quality of life of urban residents was studied by Priduam and Abdul (2012). The study operationalizes night commercial activities with the number of pubs, bars, nightclubs, night markets and restaurants. Quality of life included comfort, convenience and safety. The survey research design was used in gathering information via copies of questionnaire administered on 97 respondents from a population of 3533 persons. The study area covered about 934.38-meter radius in Bangsor Baru. Frequency counts, mean and simple percentages were used for data analysis in the study. The results showed that night commercial activities impact negatively on the quality of life of local residents. Specifically, the following were observed to include among others; pest threat and pollution arising from night commercial activities, pedestrian walking misuse by nightlife tourists, persistent increase in the volume of traffic at night times, increased transformation of household accommodation into night time investment/infrastructure etc. The study concluded that night life tourism has superlatively increased in the study area and has led to the uneven transformation and unplanned metropolis of accommodations into night time economy infrastructure. The study recommended among other things improved urban planning and nightlife economic development policies in the study area.

Theoretical Framework

The Cyclical Theory of Nightlife (CTN) was developed by Holt Jim (2006). It came into birth on the basis of the desire to adequately forecast, predict or foresee novel and innovative trends and dimensions particular to nightlife tourism vis-a-vis night time economy. The theory holds that nightlife and its paraphernalia attains an exceptional glamorous height precisely once every two decades, seven years two hundred and seventy-three and some fraction of days. According to the CTN the last glamorous height attained in nightlife across the globe was in 2005, thus the next is expected sometime in 2033 across the globe.

The theory further upholds that, when nightlife activities complete a cycle, there is an absolute and/or inevitable death or transformation, birth or re-birth of a significant if not most of the paraphernalia of nightlife and/or nighttime patronage and economy respectively. The changes that may occur at each cycle completed may include type of music, average

age of nightlife patrons, number of nighttime businesses, and so on. The rationale thus for integrating CTN is that it adequately captures the changing dimensions of nightlife tourism and nighttime economy in Lomé and Abidjan i.e the capital cities of Togo and Cote d'Ivoire respectively. For instance, in the last 3 decades precisely in 1951 the last completed nightlife cycle gave birth to the transformation of nightlife activities from the traditional format of music associated with orchestra, folk music, talking drums, live performances and congregation into a westernized influenced musical style especially among young artists in Lomé and Abidjan. This transformation gave birth to Togolese and Ivorian songs and dances like 'Wolowolo', 'Zouglou', 'Gweta', 'Laperlaper', 'Mkapye', 'Chionmichionchion', 'Zouk', 'Gbégbé', 'Prudencia', 'Zoblazo', 'Onevmillion', 'Adjamofu', 'Plingo', 'Avoude' etc. and night clubs like "Privilege" and "Saint German" in Lomé and Abidjan respectively with high rate of inbound and outbound tourists. These clubs were reinforced with advanced infrastructures with capacity to international patronage in terms of Mixed to Western music and dance, cuisine among other things. However, the metamorphosis that manifested at the completion of the nightlife cycle during the period stimulated other night life infrastructures in both cities to include, Premium Shisha, Monte-cristo, Royal nightclub, Le Simmel, Djeton Pa 2 etc. in Lomé and Blue Rock, Mixx, Alizee, Nora Metropois, Opus, Buzz etc. in Abidjan. Furthermore, the CTN will aid in predicting the future dimension, location shift, concentration, etc. within nightlife tourism and economy respectively.

The Actor-Network Theory (ANT) is a philosophical perspective of the systemic approach to social theory that attempts to capture the inter-connection of the transformative relationship that exist and/or binds human, natural and metaphysical factors in the environment. The theory is of the view that nothing exists independently and that ideas, infrastructures, beliefs, attitudes, human beings, technology etc. are in one or more forms influenced themselves either expressly or implicitly. The ANT attempts to curiously phantom the relationship of networks that consciously combine to achieve specific targets. Contributors to the development of the ANT, were scholars from the science and technology discipline, to include Michel Callon (1986), Bruno Latour (2005), John Law and John Hassard (1999). The theory can also be described as "material semiotic" largely due to the systemic attempt at juxtaposing tangible and intangible factors for exploring transformative developments in time andspace.

The rationale for integrating the ANT into the study is on the grounds that it attempts to capture the sub-components of nightlife tourism and night time economy, in terms of the inextricable relationship that expressly and/or implicitly stimulates the nightlife tourism cycle, movement, development, innovation etc.

Conceptual Classification

The broad concepts that constitute the study as well as their components will be given brief and concrete description in order to distinguish between the concepts.

Nightlife Tourism

The concept of nightlife tourism, from a realistic perspective, refers to the movement of people particularly at/or during night times or from dusk till dawn, for the

purpose of seeking one or more dimensions of physical, mental or psychological satisfaction that may be achieved either through financial exchanges for goods and/or services between patrons and night time investors. Nightlife tourism is predominantly concerned with pleasure, entertainment, leisure, fun and relation with nominal concentration on religion, arts and crafts and other tourism destination images, Cosman (2015). However, nightlife tourism describes the demographic composition, change and average age range of the movement of night time patrons within, into and outside a unique nightlife environment in time and space. It attempts to measure the degree of the intensity of both foreign and local nightlife patrons into, within and exit from night time economy (i.e. bars, nightclubs, restaurants etc.). Nightlife tourism also describes the motives for both foreign and local nightlife patrons into, within and exit from nightlife economy Jiang(2017).

Specifically, the entry, stay and exit degree of intensity of patrons in a nightlife facility describes the range of the numerical value of foreign and local patrons with dimension on a daily basis, as well as their predominant average age range, while the entry, stay and exit motives of patrons in nighttime facility describes the range of the numerical value of patrons' purchase pattern within nightlife environments, their behaviour, habits, morals, commercial sex activities, drug abuse, music preferences etc. The concept is focused on tourists whether inbound or outbound, their visit frequency and intensity as well as their motives for patronizing the nighttime economy. Conclusively, nightlife tourism refers to the cultural specificity of patrons that predominates within a unique night time economy (Chew, 2010).

Nighttime Economy

Nighttime economy describes all the indicators that capture the infrastructure, finance, labour force, public policy/regulations, nightlife led-gratification, etc. It can be measured in terms of the number of nighttime businesses operations within a night economy of a place, the revenue accruable to government due to night time business operators, the number of employment opportunities provided by night businesses, the spatial infrastructural development resulting from nightlife expansion, government policy express to nightlife tourism and so on Elvinus & Hadfield (2003). Therefore, as the indicators of a nation's economy reflect employment rate, inflation rate, fiscal and monetary policy, etc. so does nighttime economy attempt to reflect similar perspectives but with numeral values of nighttime investments, entrepreneurs, workers, revenue, taxes/ levies etc. and other prevailing conditions.

However, from the above, nighttime economy in Francophone African cities predominately revolves around nightclubs, bars and restaurants (mostly unregistered bukas) and live shows/event or festivals. These variables are the primary pull-factors for nightlife tourism and the major components of night time economy in the area, especially nightclubs, bars and restaurants. There is virtually no nightclub operating in the study area that does not have a restaurant and/or bar in close proximity. This perceived configuration attempts to evolve resulting from complementary services. Other similar services include taxi cab services, hotel accommodation, chalets and commercial sex activities. These services are perceived to agglomerate and revolve around the environs of nightclubs and bars in Lomé and Abidjan.

Hypotheses test and discussion

The study utilized data from primary sources and secondary sources. Primary sources of data were gotten from copies of questionnaire administered to inbound and outbound tourists in selected nightlife infrastructures in Lomé and Abidjan, while secondary sources were gotten from the nightlife infrastructure records of accounts on sales and other relevant development. The sample composed of 250 inbound and outbound tourists who were engaged by the researcher via a convenience sampling approach. However, the survey research design was employed in a bid to identify the similarity and difference between nightlife patrons visit dimensions and nighttime economy in Lomé and Abidjan, thus the correlation coefficient test statistic was deployed for hypothesis test.

Table 1: Correlation coefficient table for testing hypothesis 1

Variables	ΣX Σy	ΣX^2 ΣX^2	ΣXy	R
Nightlife tourism (x)	832	82161	75291	0.97
Nightlife economy (y)	981	942		

Significant level = 0.05, degree of freedom 8 critical r = .693

Evidence from the computation above proves that there is a significant relationship between nightlife tourism and nighttime economy in Lomé and Abidjan, on the grounds that the Calculated r – value of 0.97 is greater than critical r – value of .693. This therefore indicates that the quantitative increase in nightlife tourism dimensions were similar to that of nighttime economic growth in Lomé and Abidjan. This result confirms with Pooley, Hadfield & Houghton (2017) were the proceeds from nighttime economy unfolded approximately 400% annual increase in revenue resulting from similar magnitude in nightlife tourism increase.

Table 2: Correlation coefficient table for hypotheses 2

Variables	ΣX Σy	ΣX^2 Σy^2	ΣXy	R
Nightlife patrons visit (x)	1.4831	632489	48241	0.84
Nightlife economy development (y)	981	942		

Significant level = 0.05, degree of freedom =8, r = 0.693

The computed r-value of 0.84 made the investigator reject the hypothesis H2 and affirm the alternate hypothesis H2 that there is a co-variation between nightlife patrons visit dimensions and nighttime economic development in Lomé and Abidjan. This result

corroborates Elvis & Hadfield (2003) where successive increased visit of inbound and outbound nightlife patrons aided positive nighttime economic growth in the U.K.

Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

Based on the empirical discourse, theoretical baseline and conceptual clarification, which provides backings for accessing as well as achieving the specific research objectives, through the hypotheses test, Night life tourism and nighttime economy in Lomé and Abidjan can affirmably be ascribed as inextricably connected concepts that have over the period under review had similar dimensions of advancement in both the levels of inbound and outbound tourist visits, night life infrastructures, nightlife related employment opportunities, government revenue from nightlife tourism among other things. However, the francophone cities used for the investigation presented distinctive but similar patterns with respect to the variables of the study, especially captured from the cyclical theory of nightlife (CTN) that reveals major transformation in both cities at the advent of the last two completed nightlife cycle in 1951 and 2005.

Moreover, this transformation in the nightlife tourism landscape presents additional tourism dimension into the night time economy for which the research recommends for efficient exploitation as follows;

- a. The integration of culinary tourism (i.e. provision of local cuisines) in nightlife tourism landscape to enhance projection and preservation of the Togolese and Ivoirian cultures
- b. Development of principled legislations that have direct command on nightlife tourism and nighttime economy in Lomé and Abidjan, for the purpose of expanding the potency of nightlife experience among tourist populations.
- c. Amplifying nightlife public security resources to ensure safety and conducive nightlife experience especially for outbound tourists.
- d. Fiscal policy initiatives in terms of reduction in nightlife business taxes, levies etc. in order to boost entrepreneurship in the sector which holds major revenue for local countries and residents

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